

ISic0383

Funerary inscription for Vipsanius Atticus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in 1849 during excavation of the foundations of the Hospital of S.Marco (Palazzo Tezzano) , on the north side of Piazza Stesicoro

Coordinates

37.507691,15.0849354

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 350

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 30 cm

Width 29 cm

Depth 4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are written in a fluid cursive style which recalls painted letters (good examples at Pompeii).

Letter heights:

Line 1: 35-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus) · s(acrum)

2. Vipsanius · Atticus ·

4. vivos · sibi ·

5. et · suis

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Vispanius Atticus (set this up) while living for himself and
his family

Translation (it)

Consacrato agli Dei Mani. Vispanius Atticus (lo costruì) mentre era in vita per se stesso e la sua famiglia

Commentary

The formula *vivus sibi et suis* is common, reflecting the fact that Vipsanius set up a family funerary monument. The name Vipsanius is common in Catania, and it is likely that these are descendants of freedmen of Marcus Vipsanius Agrippa, the right-hand man of Octavian, who gained property in Sicily after his victory over Sextus Pompeius in 36 BC. The form *vivos*, instead of the normal *vivus*, is more common in earlier Latin.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491594

EDR 138809

EDCS 21900423

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